

INSTITUTIONAL STRENGTHENING OF OIL PALM INDEPENDENT SMALLHOLDERS SUPPLY CHAIN DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Oil palm independent smallholders need support from various efforts, one of which is through a program to strengthen independent smallholder institutions. Integrated institutions with the support of the IT Support System have influenced efforts to improve the welfare of independent smallholders, especially during the Covid 19 pandemic. This study aims to identify institutional problems, identify the role of actors in institutional strengthening and determine the design of information technology as a strengthening strategy. This research used a soft system approach (SSM) supported by qualitative and quantitative data collected from the Pelalawan and Kampar regency of Riau Province in Indonesia. The implementation of the seven steps of SSM supported by the Strategic Assumption Surfacing Technique and Analytic Network Process is based on knowledge and judgment from prominent experts. The local government is the key actor who plays an important role in strengthening independent smallholder institutions. Meanwhile, coaching and mentoring independent smallholders and cooperatives is a key program that must be implemented. Institutional strengthening of independent smallholders is a joint effort through synergy, support, and partnership between the government and business actors, from the plantation sector to oil palm processing. Institutional strengthening of independent smallholder farmers will increase the palm oil business profits and social welfare of the actors, including the smallholder farmers. The existence of information technology is believed to strengthen further the integration of roles between actors in the context of strengthening oil palm independent smallholders' institutions within supply chain strategy.

Keywords: Independent smallholder; institutional analysis; IT support system; oil palm, supply chain.

INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 has become a frightening pandemic for the world community today. The impact is very powerful and has caused fundamental changes to the entire order of life. In order to anticipate the impact of the rapid transmission of the Covid-19 pandemic, the Indonesian government continues to look for effective steps to reduce the wider impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has also had a huge impact on business and organizational life, one of which is the palm oil business sector. Various changes in organizational activities include the work system that requires workers to do more activities at home. This certainly has a considerable influence on business performance and organizational life, as is the case in the palm oil agro-industry sector. On the other hand, until now, there are still many problems faced by business actors in the oil palm sector, especially in the development of organizations and institutions of oil palm independent smallholders. Among them are related regulations and

policies, the synergy of roles between related institutions, and the lack of government support for the improvement of existing institutions that have an impact on the low level of welfare obtained by independent oil palm smallholders [1].

The oil palm plantation sector has had a positive influence on the growth of the national economy [2]. The area of oil palm plantations in Indonesia until 2017 has reached 16 million hectares, of which more than 53% of oil palm plantation land is managed by rural communities independently. Riau Province is the largest palm oil production center in Indonesia, with a production share of 22% of the total national oil palm production. Furthermore, the development of the oil palm plantation sector in Indonesia has also had a huge impact on accelerating rural economic growth in Indonesia [3]. For more than the last decade, the oil palm plantation sector has become the main source of income for improving the welfare of the community, especially those living in rural areas. This can be seen from the increasing area of oil palm plantations that are managed by farmers independently. On the other hand, the development of the oil palm plantation industry in Indonesia has also succeeded in absorbing more than 16 million workers in various sectors, both the plantation sector and the palm oil agro-industry.

Socially, the development of the national oil palm industry plays a very important role in rural development, poverty reduction, equitable distribution of economic development, as well as improvement of income inequality and development [4]. The dependence of rural communities on oil palm plantations has made oil palm the main source of income for the economy and welfare. The high dependence of rural communities on the results of oil palm plantations is feared to lead to high vulnerability of community household livelihoods because they only expect one source of income. As a result, if there is a fluctuation in the price of palm oil, it can cause the community to lose a lot of income, as has happened until now [5]. Poverty and underdevelopment of rural communities are generally caused by several factors and conditions. There are three patterns and conditions for the formation of villages as a result of the development of the oil palm plantation sector, namely: 1) villages with areas that are naturally isolated and underdeveloped due to the lack of development and have not been touched by the reach of transportation infrastructure, 2) villages with the condition of the area of ex-logging practices where the land is not utilized optimally, and 3) the village with the condition of the area of the former mining process such as mining of coal, tin, and other mineral resources [4].

Rural development is one of the focuses of development policies in Indonesia. There are three main foundations for the stipulation of the policy, among others [6]: 1) the majority of the population in Indonesia lives in rural areas, 2) the largest labor force is also found in rural areas with professions as mostly farmers, and 3) the number of poor people in Indonesia generally lives in the countryside. So rural development in Indonesia must be focused on improving village welfare and alleviating the poor. One of the solutions that can be offered in order to realize the rural development plans and policies is through the development of independent villages based on the potential that exists in each rural area. The independence of the village in developing the potential of the existing area is very dependent on the efforts that can be made jointly among stakeholders such as the government, the private sector, and the community as

beneficiaries. The synergy between roles must be realized through various empowerment programs for various institutional aspects and the potential of human resources.

Currently, oil palm independent smallholders dominate more than 40% of the total number of oil palm smallholders in Indonesia [7]. Generally, they are institutionalized by forming farmer associations, such as the Joint Business Group (KUB), Farmers Forum, and Farmers Group Association (Gapoktan) to the form of larger organizational institutions in the form of cooperatives. However, various management problems are still so large that joint efforts and support from all parties, both government, business actors, and educational institutions, are needed in accordance with their respective roles in the context of synergizing and collaborating to support efforts to strengthen independent smallholder institutions. This research related to strengthening the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders seeks to answer two problems that are currently being faced by oil palm independent smallholder institutions, including first: the problem of the current weak institutional governance of independent smallholders and second: the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic which has provided many benefits, influence on organizational life. To be able to provide alternative solutions, various stages have been carried out in this research, starting from identifying the existing problems related to the current institutional governance of oil palm independent smallholders to the impacts caused by the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak. Furthermore, through the development of a conceptual model that describes the existing conditions related to the relationship and role of each interested party, it will be tried to obtain an alternative solution for strengthening the institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders. As an alternative, the proposal offered is to involve digitalization technology that contains various application menus that support various administrative processes, performance assessments, and digital transactions. Through the development of this digitalization-based application, it is hoped that it can have a positive impact in supporting various management and decision-making activities in the core organizations that are the object of this study and, at the same time, become an approach to strengthening the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders.

However, despite the efforts of independent smallholders to improve their welfare through participation in an institution, not all of them can run well as they expect. Not infrequently also happens. The organizations that they have built independently are not able to develop properly and even have to disband due to various factors. Some of the causes of the undeveloped organization such as oil palm self-help cooperatives include: 1) lack of organizational management capabilities of the board, 2) lack of financial management transparency that triggers members' distrust of the board, 3) administrative and bureaucratic processes which are sometimes felt to be very hindering efforts farmers in meeting various needs, and 4) there are more promising offers from competitors, in this case, middlemen who are generally more flexible in conducting transactions, sales and payments (Raharja et al., 2020).

There are various reasons behind the institutional problems of independent smallholders. The role and support of various parties are very much needed in order to strengthen the existing independent smallholder organizations and institutions. The synergy between stakeholders is very much needed in contributing benefits according to their respective roles. The objectives

of this study include: 1) To get a real picture of institutional problems in the area of observation, 2) To get the involvement of each actor and their role in the current existing institutions, 3) To find out the basic assumptions in order to determine the key elements of institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders; 4) To design digital-based applications as an effort to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders.

METHODOLOGY

1.1 Research Framework

An independent smallholder is one of the professions that many rural communities in Indonesia are currently engaged in. The same is true for the oil palm plantation sector. However, due to various limitations and existing conditions, independent smallholders are still in a weak position compared to other business actors in the palm oil supply chain. The efforts to support in order to improve the bargaining position of independent oil palm smallholders must be carried out, one of which is through the establishment of institutions or strengthening of existing organizations and institutions. Strengthening independent smallholder institutions certainly requires support from various parties in accordance with their respective roles, both from the government, oil palm plantation companies, and associations of oil palm independent smallholders or from universities. Through the joint synergy between roles that are poured into a real program, it is hoped that an independent oil palm smallholder organization will be able to become an organization that supports the improvement of the welfare of independent smallholders in particular and the improvement of the village economy in general. The framework of thought in this study can be presented in Figure 1. This study seeks to build a system that can accommodate various needs in order to strengthen the independent smallholder institutional organization in the village. A collaborative role in a partnership program between the village government and various business actors engaged in the oil palm plantation sector within the village scope is expected to be the main source of improving the income and welfare of independent smallholders and, at the same time, increasing the level of the rural economy in general.

Figure 1: Research framework diagram

1.2 Research Stages

In general, this research was conducted by applying the seven steps of Soft System Methodology (SSM). SSM is an approach to a systemic study through the use of systems models [9]. SSM can provide key techniques and basic theories that are important to identify and define a problem and, at the same time, explore the relevance between the relationships of system components in a broader conceptualization [10]. SSM is a holistic approach to solving complex and unstructured problems [11]. In overcoming an unstructured problem, systems thinking approach is needed that is able to see aspects of the interrelationships between activities carried out by various interested parties, from input to output levels. System thinking includes the process of thinking with a goal, end result, and target in mind, which includes the interaction of elements, components, and subsystems to form a system. SSM is a systematic approach that applies seven steps of analysis, starting from identifying institutional and village problems to an action plan for implementing the institutional model built. The important stages of SSM can be described as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Soft System Methodology (SSM) Stage Diagram

1. Situational analysis of the existing problems, in this case, the existing institutional problems in the area of observation of oil palm independent smallholders in an effort to realize village independence. An important question that needs to be answered in this early stage is how the real situation is related to institutional relations between various parties from the strategic level to the operational and technical level.
2. Knowing what problems exist in various interested parties seen from the needs, roles of activities, and responsibilities of each. The output of this stage is in the form of a Rich Picture, which describes the relationship between one party and another.
3. Defines each group role into an approach called CATWOE (Client or Customers, Actors, Transformations, Weltanschauung, Owner, and Environmental Constraints).
4. Designing a conceptual model that explains the relationship between activities and other activities. The conceptual model describes the input-process-output relationship between one activity and another.
5. Develop an agenda of activities that will be carried out in real terms in the field and, at the same time, make comparisons between the real world and the conceptual model that has been designed previously.
6. Define possible changes to be implemented. Some of the changes that may occur include changes in procedures, changes in structure, or changes in attitudes and culture in the form of changes in values, norms, or ways of thinking.
7. Take corrective action, especially on the model that has been built.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Data collection in this study took a case study in the Riau province in Indonesia. This area has the largest oil palm plantation area in Indonesia. Then, the sample selection of independent oil

palm farmers was selected in two districts that have dominant plantation lands in Riau Province, including Kampar and Pelalawan Regencies. In this area, it has an independent oil palm farmer community. Each district is selected by a community of independent oil palm smallholders to be the object of study in strengthening the oil palm independent smallholder organization. Thus, the design of this study adopts a case study approach to explore the phenomena that occur in oil palm independent smallholders. Case study research can analyze phenomena in detail to reveal an event and be able to generalize the results in the decision-making process [12], [13]. Various data were collected from various sources, both primary data and secondary data, for the purposes of analysis. The primary data in this study is in the form of expert opinion data related to the level of interest between elements in order to find out the main elements that are key in efforts to strengthen oil palm independent smallholders' institutions. Meanwhile, to complete the description of the problems studied, data were also obtained from various written sources or documents that had been presented, sourced from reports on the observed organizations, and the results of literacy studies from various relevant sources. This study involves as many as five experts who have provided their responses to the influence of various elements on the key factors in strengthening the institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders. Determination of experts is done through the application of the purposive sampling technique, which is inclusively selected based on the suitability of expert knowledge with the main focus of study, knowledge, and experience of experts seen from education or the various studies they have produced as well as the professionalism of experts in carrying out their roles and responsibilities in an organization the profession they have been in.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

1.3 Strategic Assumptions Surfacing And Testing (Sast) Method

System design and implementation in the field require some basic assumptions to be considered in order to be easily applied in the real world. It was determined these basic assumptions require various considerations that need to be considered so that the implementation of the institutional system can run in accordance with the desired system output. The design of basic assumptions in the application of the system in the field can be designed with a conceptual framework proposed by [14], hereinafter known as Strategic Assumptions Surfacing and Testing (SAST). Determining assumptions through SAST, focusing on critical and basic aspects to ensure that the system thought can be applied to systems in the real world (Raharja et al., 2020). The SAST approach in implementing the system in the real world has also been proven to be able to identify conflicts of interest between stakeholders in the system to be analyzed and resolved together in a coordinated manner [15]. The SAST approach in system implementation is not a single approach that should be used. SAST needs to be juxtaposed with other approaches because, in its position, SAST only facilitates exploring the various needs of stakeholders and entities in the system, ensure information is provided to all parties and design the desired system output after transformation.

Furthermore, Barabba & Mitroff (2014) states that SAST is able to determine the key stakeholders in the system and their main roles that influence decision-making in the system. With these characteristics, previous studies have been able to take advantage of the reliability of SAST for system transformation. In its application, Easton et al. (1992) used and developed SAST to identify key stakeholders and their assumptions in small groups, Pradini et al. (2016) applied SAST to strengthen the institution's position in its role in food sustainability, and Raharja et al., (2020) develop basic assumptions to strengthen the position of independent smallholders in the oil palm supply chain. Other studies also success proved to strengthen actors through supply chain strategy[19]–[21]. The important role of SAST in determining the basic assumptions and key stakeholders in system transformation is based on five basic principles, namely: adversarial, participative, integrative, and supportive (Barabba & Mitroff, 2014). In order to determine the basic assumptions and key stakeholders, the following are the steps that need to be carried out and considered: 1) Formation of discussion groups; 2) Discussion group to determine assumption surfacing and rating; 3) Debate in groups to determine, 4) Assumptions that are important and certain assumptions will become the center of system transformation policy; 5) Assumptions that lie in an important position about uncertainty, therefore require supervision and research; 6) Assumptions that lie in the other two quadrants can be eliminated, however, if there is the time it can be discussed again in the group.

1.4 Analytical Network Process (Anp) Method

Analytical Network Process (ANP) is a new theory developed from the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) proposed by (Saaty, 1987). The idea of developing ANP comes from the limited ability of AHP to define a problem. As is known, the hierarchy compiled in AHP aims to determine the priority of alternative strategies. This means that the selection of strategic priorities is only determined by the criteria, and there is no reciprocal influence from strategy to criteria. ANP allows solving complex problems that are impossible to solve with AHP. The existence of a feedback feature and being more adaptive and does not have to be top-down makes ANP more flexible in defining problems. The ANP approach has the ability to formulate a comprehensive strategy compared to the AHP. If in AHP, problems are simplified through a hierarchy, ANP describes the real world as a network. The network is able to describe the problem more precisely because the relationship between components is more precise (Saaty & Vargas, 2013).

ANP's ability to structure and solve complex problems has been applied to various sectors and previous research. Several ANP applications for decision making have been applied to sustainable city development policies [24], improving industrial performance [25], identifying challenges in the application of industry 4.0 [26], to formulating strategies in the supply chain [27]. The ANP assessment uses a relative rating model on a scale of 1 – 9. This assessment can be given if the elements in the ANP network are known with certainty (Saaty, 2005). Several relationships between elements in the ANP determine the aspects to be assessed relative and pairwise comparison. As an illustration, the form of a network that can be designed for the design of the ANP model in prioritizing elements can be seen in Figure 3. In Figure 3, it can be explained that C1, C2, C3, and C4 are networks that contain nodes or important indicators

in capacity building and institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders. Between nodes and networks can be connected by inner dependent or outer dependent. The relationship between nodes and the network can determine the main aspects that need to be considered in the preparation.

Figure 3: Flowchart of ANP

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Steps 1 And 2: Existing Conditions and Institutional Problems of Independent Smallholders

Research on the institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders in rural Indonesia has been carried out in Riau Province, particularly in two oil palm centers, namely Kampar Regency and Pelalawan Regency. In both areas, oil palm plantations have developed with an area of 407,139 Ha and 393,324 Ha, respectively [29]. Of the total area of oil palm plantations in Kampar Regency, 55 % or 226,085 Ha are owned by rural communities, while in Pelalawan Regency, 30.4% or 119,612 Ha are oil palm plantations owned by rural communities. Based on the results of opinion polls with oil palm plantation business actors or the government, various problems related to institutions that exist in the two districts have been identified, including:

- a. There is no synergy between the roles of government institutions and business actors, especially institutions that support the bargaining position of independent smallholders in the oil palm supply chain.
- b. The performance of each business actor is not yet known, including independent smallholders, intermediary traders, cooperatives, and oil palm companies.
- c. The oil palm supply chain is long enough to have a significant effect on the high variability of FFB prices among oil palm plantation business actors.
- d. The existence of intermediary traders and the absence of regulations that require them to be institutionalized have had a considerable influence on the selling price of FFB.

- e. The role of cooperatives as a core institution in developing and strengthening oil palm independent smallholders is not yet maximized.
- f. There are still doubts among independent smallholders whether they want to be institutionalized or want to join in an institutional form such as joint business groups (KUB), farmer groups associations (Gapoktan), or cooperatives.
- g. There is still a lack of support and contribution from the government, associations, or oil palm companies in an effort to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders.
- h. The awareness of business actors, especially independent smallholders or cooperatives, is still low on the importance of oil palm plantation certification.
- i. The lack of good administration of data collection and management of cooperative organizations is due to various limitations such as managerial ability, quality of human resources, or information technology support.
- j. There has been no transparency and unified price between each business actor, whether at the level of independent smallholders, intermediary traders, cooperatives, or oil palm companies.
- k. The unavailability of technology that can support the government's efforts to carry out the function of control and supervision of the business processes of business actors in the oil palm plantation sector.
- l. There is still a lack of knowledge among business actors, especially oil palm independent smallholders, regarding policies and regulations that can guarantee legal certainty (legality) of oil palm plantations.
- m. There is no best mechanism for assessing the traceability of FFB origin from oil palm plantations owned by independent smallholders.

In Figure 4, a conceptual model of the institutional form of oil palm independent smallholders has been presented in each of the observed areas. The institutional forms of the two observed areas have different characteristics from each other. This is due to various factors such as the business orientation to be achieved, support from external parties for existing institutions, as well as the joint efforts that have been made by each business actor in strengthening the existing oil palm independent smallholder institutions.

Figure 4: Existing Model of Oil Palm Independent Smallholders Institution in Kampar Regency, Riau

Step 3: Determining the Root of the Problem (Root Definition)

Institutions of independent oil palm smallholders involve many parties with their respective roles. Institutions of independent oil palm smallholders consist of actors from the government, associations, or business actors along the palm oil supply chain. Each actor has a role and responsibility in efforts to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders. The actors involved in strengthening the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders are presented in Table I. Then, Figure 5 describes the Rich Picture of Institutional Problems.

Table 1: Stakeholders in strengthening independent smallholder institutions, their responsibilities and roles

No	Actors	Role in oil palm independent smallholders institutional
1	Independent Smallholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get involved in a formal institution • Meet the various requirements for membership of the formal institutions that are followed • Actively participate in complying with all the provisions contained in the articles of association and by-laws of formal organizations • Contribute to business and organization development
2	Formal Organization Manager (Independent Smallholders Group or Cooperative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out administrative functions such as member recruitment, data collection, management of organizational members, reporting and so on • Carry out managerial functions of the organization as a whole, starting from planning, management, resource mobilization and control • Carry out the organization's business functions, such as determining prices and fees, carrying out transactions by buying and selling with members or with other business partners, distributing supplies, transportation and storage • Carry out the function of coaching, empowering and strengthening all members of the organization. • Developing the organization through cooperative relationships and partnerships with various parties, both with the government, companies, associations, companies and certification bodies.
3	Palm Oil Company	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide support for coaching, mentoring and funding in various fields to farmers and cooperatives as a form of implementing corporate social responsibility • Establishing mutually reinforcing cooperative and partnership relationships with cooperatives and farmer groups • Providing easy access to information, especially related to benchmark prices as a form of transparency in transactions
4	Independent Smallholder Association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out administrative functions in the member recruitment process and data collection • Carrying out the function as a facilitator in coaching and mentoring in various fields) which is held jointly between associations with companies or other institutions • Initiating cooperation between Independent Smallholders/ Gapoktan/ Cooperatives with certification bodies or with oil palm companies • As a mediator to resolve problems or conflicts that occur between members or with the company
5	Local Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out the planning function in designing and stipulating various rules, regulations and policies related to business and trade, fostering and managing oil palm institutions • Carrying out the functions of supervision, monitoring and evaluation in the context of improving current and future institutional governance • Carry out the function of directing, delegating and disseminating various information, rules, regulations and policies that have been prepared • Carry out development functions in various fields of coaching and empowerment as well as funding for farmers or cooperatives

No	Actors	Role in oil palm independent smallholders institutional
6	Certification Body (ISPO/Rspo)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out the planning function in setting certification standards, guidelines, SOPs and indicators of success • Carry out various coaching and mentoring activities related to various existing standards and indicators • Carry out an assessment process for every effort and process that has been carried out by each actor according to applicable standards and guidelines • Carry out monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of each standard and indicator in order to improve the business performance of each actor in the future
7	University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out relevant research in efforts to develop and strengthen independent smallholder institutions • Carry out a role in providing education, coaching, mentoring as part of the task of community service • Become a mediator and facilitator in connecting the needs between actors, both between business actors and the government
8	Other Institutions (Banking, National Palm Oil Fund)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing support in the form of funding that leads to improvement, development and strengthening of independent smallholder institutional governance • Providing easy access and information for each actor in an effort to get funding and coaching support

Figure 5: Rich picture of Institutional problems

Step 4: Design a Conceptual Model for Strengthening Independent Smallholder Institutions

The conceptual model is a diagram illustrating the interrelationships between interested parties, particularly related to efforts to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders. The conceptual model diagram of the institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Conceptual model diagram of institutional strengthening

Step 5: Comparison of the Model with the Real System

In the context of strengthening independent smallholder institutions, various assumptions are needed that lead to institutional strengthening efforts, both in the context of organizational management, improvement of roles or partnerships, and cooperation between actors. The assumptions made were obtained through various identification processes and opinion polls for each expert involved in this research. Then, the assumptions built are evaluated through comparative analysis based on the level of importance and level of certainty. The level of importance is a parameter that shows how much the assumption affects institutional strengthening efforts. In contrast, the level of certainty can be interpreted as the level of possibility for the implementation of these assumptions in the real world. Based on the opinion polls that have been carried out by the experts, this research has obtained as many as 13 basic assumptions that affect efforts to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders. The 13 assumptions are presented in Table II. Based on the SAST analysis, each assumption has been classified into a Cartesian diagram, as shown in Figure 7. The results of the SAST analysis have found that there are three main assumptions that are most important and possible to be applied. The SAST analysis has recommended three basic assumptions as

the most likely strategy to be applied in order to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders. The three assumptions are presented in Figure 8.

Table 2: Basic assumptions for institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders

Code	Assumptions
A1	There are policies and mandates related to ISPO certification that are more binding and profitable for supply chain actors (independent farmers, farmer cooperatives/institutions, and palm oil company)
A2	The existence of regulations and policies on FFB price incentives from independent smallholder oil palm plantations that are members of ISPO-certified institutions
A3	The realization of policies that can clarify the position and role of traders/platforms in the palm oil supply chain
A4	The establishment of harmonization and collaboration of the roles of Central/Local Government SKPDs related to efforts to strengthen the oil palm supply chain institutions
A5	The increasing role of the government in providing funding assistance for the preparation of ISPO certification for independent smallholders and oil palm independent smallholders cooperatives
A6	There is a collaborative partnership between associations and PKS in fostering supply chain actors (independent farmers, traders, cooperatives) in cultivation, harvesting, post-harvest, and transportation activities to improve quality and productivity
A7	There is funding support from the government and the private sector in realizing the data collection program (STDB) for Oil Palm Independent Smallholders
A8	Increasing the role of independent smallholder associations in efforts to foster and empower oil palm independent smallholders
A9	The existence of a coaching program in various fields with sufficient financial support from the local government for oil palm independent smallholders
A10	There is a social awareness fund from oil palm companies to increase the capacity of oil palm independent smallholders
A11	The existence of synergy and business cooperation between cooperatives/institutions of cooperative oil palm farmers and village business entities (BUMDES)
A12	There is clarity (transparency), traceability and fairness of prices and quality standards of FFB among business actors
A13	There is a need to build long-term contracts between oil palm business actors (farmers, cooperatives and palm oil company) that refer to quality standards and agreed selling prices for FFB

Figure 7: SAST Cartesian Diagram

Figure 8: Three main assumptions in efforts to strengthen independent smallholder institutions

Furthermore, in order to determine priority programs in an effort to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders, analysis has also been carried out through the ANP approach. In this analysis, as many as four factors consisting of actors, enablers, obstacles, and programs are compared with each other in order to obtain priority elements of each factor. The relationship between factors can be seen in Figure 9. The results of the comparative analysis that has been carried out have found several priority elements of each factor being compared. Through the calculation of scores and rankings, it is known the priority elements of strengthening, among others for the actor factor; the main element that has a key role in institutional strengthening is cooperatives or farmer groups. Meanwhile, the key enabling factor in institutional strengthening is support from the government. Furthermore, the key element that can hinder efforts to strengthen institutions is the absence of synergy between supply chain stakeholders to partner, while the main program that must be built in the context

of institutional strengthening is coaching and mentoring. The results of the overall ANP comparison analysis are presented in Table III. The results of the ANP have shown several key elements that are priorities for the institutional efforts of oil palm independent smallholders. Then, Table IV describes expected changes and activities.

Figure 9: Analysis of Network Process (ANP) of institutional strengthening element

Table 3: ANP scores and rankings for each actor, enabler, obstacles and institutional strengthening program for oil palm independent smallholders

Cluster	Elements	Score	Ranking
Actors	1. Local government	0,15564	4
	2. Smallholder association	0,16339	3
	3. Palm oil company	0,22171	2
	4. Cooperative	0,25915	1
	5. Oil palm independent smallholder	0,14686	5
	6. intermediate distributor	0,05324	6
Enabler	1. Actor's motivation for cooperation/synergy	0,32233	2
	2. Government support	0,41297	1
	3. Coordination and transparency in reference pricing	0,19027	3
	4. Support of rural enterprises	0,07443	4
Obstacles	1. Limited experience and managerial ability of cooperatives	0,22455	2
	2. There is no synergy between supply chain stakeholders to partner up	0,42811	1
	3. Presence of middlemen/collectors	0,03611	5
	4. Lack of availability of extension workers for plantations	0,09857	4
	5. Limited access to information	0,21266	3
Program	1. Certification of oil palm plantations and organizations (ISPO/RSPO)	0,2117	2
	2. Coaching and mentoring independent smallholders and cooperatives	0,39114	1
	3. Digital contract initiation and implementation	0,11421	4
	4. Application of supply chain information system	0,17807	3
	5. Strengthening the synergy of cooperatives and rural business entities	0,10488	5

Table 4: Expected changes and activities

No	Organizational and Institutional Elements	Existing Condition	Expected Condition	Activities
1	Cooperative membership data collection	<p>Membership data is incomplete and not well organized</p> <p>The data collection system is generally still manual</p>	<p>Membership data is getting more complete and well organized</p> <p>More computerized data collection system</p>	<p>Data collection through the use of instruments</p> <p>Inputting of profile data of farmers, traders, cooperatives and palm oil mills into the information system application that was built</p>
2	Price transparency among actors	<p>Not all independent smallholders can access government FFB pricing</p> <p>Price margin information is only known by a few actors</p> <p>Information on marketing costs is only known between two groups of actors (e.g., Cooperatives/ Traders to palm oil companies)</p> <p>The cooperative has not been able to explain in detail the use of the FFB discount that is collected for each transaction process</p>	<p>There is information on the price of government decisions that is up-to-date and can be accessed at any time by every actor</p> <p>The realization of price transparency among business actors and clarity on the use of cost allocations from FFB discounted prices by cooperatives</p>	<p>Provision of a menu containing information related to the latest price information that is connected to the price data set by the government</p>
3	Transaction	<p>The suitability of the measurement of the scales is not accurate which can be detrimental to one of the parties</p> <p>The buying and selling system are manual with inconsistent procedures</p> <p>There has been no effort from palm oil</p>	<p>Scales need government supervision and calibration of scales needs to be done before buying and selling transactions are carried out</p> <p>Buying and selling transactions are more procedural, neat and transparent</p>	<p>Availability of the Digital Transaction menu on an information system application that is built</p>

No	Organizational and Institutional Elements	Existing Condition	Expected Condition	Activities
		companies to provide farmer share to farmers	There is a farmer share mechanism from some of the profits obtained by PKS to independent farmers	
4	Supply Chain Performance	<p>The absence of information related to the performance of each actor makes it difficult for the government to determine the performance improvement program for business actors</p> <p>The determination of the price margin is generally dominated by palm oil companies</p> <p>Independent smallholders have not been able to properly measure the ratio between profits and costs</p>	<p>Obtaining performance scores from each business actor from the level of farmers, traders, cooperatives to palm oil mills</p> <p>Pricing should be based on an agreement between independent smallholders and oil palm companies in a fair and transparent grading</p> <p>The results of the calculation of the ratio between costs and benefits for independent smallholders are obtained</p>	Availability of supply chain performance measurement menu from farmer, trader, cooperative and factory level on information system application
5	FFB Traceability	There is no technology in data collection for traceability of the origin of FFB, both in terms of FFB seeds and the location of origin of FFB	Knowing the origin of the fruit from each supplier TBS integrated, clear and transparent	Availability of traceability menu on information system applications that are built

No	Organizational and Institutional Elements	Existing Condition	Expected Condition	Activities
6	Monitoring and Evaluation	Stakeholders have not been able to know the level of supply chain performance of each business actor, making it difficult to determine the coaching program	Obtaining access to supply chain performance information from each business actor by local governments, national funding institutions and other relevant institutions	Providing access to the use of information system applications to local governments (related work units), BDPKS and IPB as application developers

Steps 6 And 7: Expected Changes And Institutional Strengthening Strategies

In order to strengthen an organization, of course, requires an integrated information system. In this case, strengthening the institutional organization of the Joint Business Group requires an integrated information system between stakeholders. The goal is to convey information transparently to all users as needed, improve communication between stakeholders, and as a control tool in conducting intensive performance measurements. Digital contracts in the palm oil supply chain are not simply implemented without clear objectives. For this reason, the research team has explored through brainstorming supply chain actors in the field and found several needs. This needs analysis is the first step for designing digital contracts to suit the needs in the field. The research team has identified three main requirements that must be adopted in the design of digital contracts, namely: a) The need for digital data for easy recording, storage, and contract history; b) Transparency of the deviation of the selling price and buying price of FFB; c) Ability to see the contract fulfillment process more transparently, as well as evaluate the contract. The results of the needs analysis are then used as the basis for designing the basic framework for developing a digital contract prototype. The development of a digital contract framework in the palm oil supply chain involves three main actors, namely independent smallholders, cooperatives, and PKS. The implementation of digital contracts in the field begins with contract initiation, contract execution, monitoring and evaluation, and contract reporting. The mechanism and framework of digital contracts can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Digital contract framework and relationships

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study found a variety of issues and recommendations as a strategy for institutional strengthening of independent smallholders of palm oil in the past 19 Covid this pandemic. The study has identified as many as 13 main institutional problems of existing independent smallholders, where these institutional problems are an accumulation of problems from each business actor ranging from independent smallholders, intermediary traders, cooperatives, and oil palm companies to the government. This study has also found 13 basic assumptions in efforts to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders. Of the 13 assumptions, three main assumptions have been set as key elements, including a) The establishment of harmonization of roles between the government and efforts to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders; b) Increasing the role of associations in the development and empowerment of oil palm independent smallholders, and c) Funding support from the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) program. The development of information technology as a supporter of decision making has been able to have a positive impact on efforts to strengthen the institutions of oil palm independent smallholders during the Covid 19 pandemic. Integration of management processes into an application, providing important menus such as registration, data storage, tracing the origin of FFB, digital contracts, and so on, really help business processes between business actors and, at the same time, become a monitoring tool for the government in its efforts to provide various supports to palm oil business actors.

This research has succeeded in formulating a strategy for institutional strengthening of oil palm independent smallholders. Then, there are several strategic assumptions that are formulated in an effort to strengthen the institutions of independent oil palm smallholders. However, this is still limited to the formulation of several selected strategic assumptions to provide optimal results for institutional strengthening. Further research is suggested to carry out a simulation

approach to several selected strategy assumptions related to the application of information technology as decision support. Thus, the empowerment of oil palm independent smallholders can be carried out more effectively and efficiently during the Covid 19 pandemic.

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